

QUALITY BY DESIGN APPROACHES (QbD) IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF HYDROGEL-BASED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

In drug delivery systems based on hydrogel, the Quality by Design (QbD) strategy promotes proactive planning through the systematic design, optimization, and control of formulation factors to ensure product quality and performance. To enhance the development of high-quality pharmaceutical products, the FDA embraced the Quality by Design (QbD) approach in the pharmaceutical sector, to achieve a comprehensive understanding of how material attributes and process parameters influence the quality and performance of the final products. Scientists are intrigued by hydrogel drug delivery systems due to a variety of reasons, such as high-water content, biocompatibility with biological products, structural variability, and the potential for administration via multiple routes. Incorporating QbD principles into hydrogel formulation ensures that the drug's physicochemical characteristics and release pattern are modulated to attain desired therapeutic targets. Such a strategy focuses on the determination of critical quality attributes (CQAs), critical process parameters (CPPs),

and design space that is robust, thereby enabling the prediction of the result and the reduction of variability during manufacturing. Through tools like Design of Experiments (DOE), risk assessment, and sophisticated characterization methods, QbD facilitates the development of hydrogels that have ideal drug release rates, improved stability, and site-specific delivery. In this summary, we describe the place of the QbD approach in hydrogel-based drug delivery systems research and development, emphasizing key applications and means of applying the

approach. We further address the challenges associated with it, such as the requirement for thorough characterization, regulatory approval, and scale-up from laboratory to industrial. Ultimately, QbD offers a structured framework for designing and manufacturing hydrogel-based drug delivery systems, ensuring product consistency and therapeutic efficacy.

KEYWORDS: QbD; Hydrogel; Drug Delivery; Quality Target Product Profile; Critical Quality Attributes; Critical Material Attributes; Critical Process Parameter; Design of Experiment.

INTRODUCTION

This brief review focuses on hydrogels, which are water-swollen polymer networks. Hydrophilic gels, commonly referred to as hydrogels, consist of polymer chain networks that utilize water as their dispersion medium.^[1] Because of their high-water content and superior transport qualities, hydrogels exhibit flexibility similar to natural tissue. They are biocompatible, easily modifiable, and capable of delivering growth factors over time.^[2] Hydrogels and drug delivery systems are generally categorized as either natural or synthetic. Natural hydrogels encompass substances like chitosan, alginate, fibrin, gelatine, and hyaluronic acid, while synthetic ones include poly (ethylene glycol) and poly (vinyl alcohol).^[3] Additionally, a third category that includes semi-synthetic hydrogels, such as gelatine methacryloyl hydrogels, which originate from gelatin and are chemically modified with synthetic methacryloyl groups.^[4]

Hydrogels can be chemically stable or rapidly degraded, depending on their structure.^[5] Hydrogels possess distinct characteristics, including reliable biocompatibility, adjustable mechanical strength and degradability, responsiveness to different stimuli, and compatibility with both hydrophilic and hydrophobic therapeutic compounds. They have advanced biomedical applications, including drug delivery, tissue regeneration, 3D cell cultures, in vitro diagnostics, and stem cell-related studies.^[6] Despite their potential, hydrogel carriers face notable obstacles in terms of production and drug entrapment capabilities. These challenges include controlling gelation temperature, drug release rate, uniform drug content, product appearance, elasticity, mechanical strength, gelation time, and other factors. To create a high-performing hydrogel-based pharmaceutical system, it's crucial to have a solid method for managing these problems.^[7]

This modern approach, QbD, strengthens design control, simplifies problem-solving, and automizes manual testing. To achieve failsafe quality, a planned method is used to ensure finished product compatibility with all components and production procedures, rather than only checking the end product.^[8] QbD provides an understanding of upstream throughout the development process. The issue of top quality is thoroughly investigated, and the underlying cause is swiftly pinpointed. In order to comply with QbD, all process variables and formulation features must be identified, and any modifications that could impact the final product standards must be detailed.^[8] QbD acts as a worldwide regulatory standard that supports proactive planning of manufacturing processes and control strategies to consistently achieve desired product outcomes.^[9] The ICH Q8 to Q11 guidelines provide a comprehensive overview of the pharmaceutical development concepts central to QbD. The Four ICH guidelines that provide insights into quality-by-design and related elements are Q8 – Pharmaceutical Development, Q9 – Quality Risk Management, Q10 – Pharmaceutical Quality Systems, and Q11 – Development and Manufacture of Drug Substances. The ICH guideline Q8 is divided into two segments: the first part addresses pharmaceutical development, while the second part serves as an appendix detailing the concepts and tools of QbD. The ICH Q8(R2) guideline defines QbD as “A systematic approach in development that begins with predefined objectives and emphasizes product and process understanding and process control, based on sound science and quality risk management”.^[10] Comprehensive instructions for implementing QRM methodologies are provided in ICH guideline Q9.^[10] Improving the development strategy requires continuous product and process optimization. The ICH Q10 - Pharmaceutical Quality System^[11] highlights the need for continuous improvement and lifecycle management to maintain consistent and high-quality product delivery. ICHQ8(R2) addresses pharmaceutical development, whereas ICHQ11 "Development and Manufacture of Drug Substances" guides applying ICHQ8(R2) concepts and quality risk management to drug substance formulation design and production.^[11]

This review focuses on QbD approaches for creating hydrogel-based drug delivery systems. QbD is a modern approach increasingly adopted within pharmaceutical production for maintaining uniform product quality through the streamlining of both formulation design and troubleshooting processes.^[8] The QbD prioritizes the intentional design of drug formulations and production methods to reliably deliver the desired quality attributes.^[12] This concept centers on assessing how alterations in manufacturing and formulation variables influence the critical characteristics of the end product.^[8]

A clear understanding of QbD's key principles and elements is vital for analyzing and developing hydrogel-based pharmaceutical products. Designing and optimizing a pharmaceutical product through the QbD framework begins with outlining the target product characteristics (QTPPs) and subsequently determining the critical quality attributes (CQAs). Based on prior research and experience, list the critical material attributes (CMAs) and critical process parameters (CPPs) that affect CQAs. Due to their large number, screening for some effective elements is necessary (Risk assessment). Several parameters are selected based on screening and risk assessment. An experiment should be planned using DoE to observe how different variables affect CQAs. The results can then be analyzed statistically to understand the connections between them. The design space provides proper limits for each variable to avoid large changes in the final product. This allows for optimization based on these limits. Based on research findings, control mechanisms for pharmaceutical manufacture should be developed.^[2]

Figure 1: Quality by design (QbD) key elements.

This review individually discusses each component of the QbD approach, starting with a general overview of its concept and the method of implementation. How each element is addressed in the selected studies on hydrogel-based drug delivery systems is briefly discussed in the text and systematically summarized in the tables. This review categorizes them based on the routes of drug administration and the specific drug delivery systems employed.^[6]

OVERVIEW OF HYDROGEL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS

Classification of Hydrogels

Hydrogels are classified based on origin (natural, synthetic, semi-synthetic), polymer type (homopolymer, copolymer, multipolymer), structure (amorphous, semi-crystalline, crystalline), cross-linking method (physical or chemical), electric charge (non-ionic, cationic, anionic, amphoteric, or zwitterionic), degradability (biodegradable or non-biodegradable), and responsiveness to stimuli such as pH, temperature, ionic strength, and electromagnetic radiation.^[13,14] (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Systematic Classification of Hydrogels According to Source Origin, Polymer Type, Charge, Cross-Linking Method, Structural Arrangement, Responsiveness, and Degradability.

Drug Release Mechanisms^[15]

Diffusion-controlled: Drug release from hydrogels primarily occurs through a diffusion-controlled process. Fick's law of diffusion is often used to model this mechanism, which may involve fixed or variable diffusion coefficients. Drug diffusivity is generally measured through experimental methods or estimated using theoretical models based on free volume concepts, hydrodynamic behaviour, or obstruction theory.

Chemically controlled: Chemically controlled release involves the liberation of drug molecules through chemical reactions within the drug delivery system. In hydrogel-based systems, this usually occurs via polymer degradation caused by hydrolysis or enzymatic

processes, along with reversible or irreversible interactions between the drug and the polymeric network. The release rate can be modulated as hydrogels undergo either surface or bulk erosion, depending on the surrounding environmental conditions. Additionally, introducing drug-binding groups into hydrogels can influence the release rate by altering binding equilibria.

Swelling-controlled: Drug release is considered swelling-controlled when diffusion proceeds more rapidly than hydrogel swelling. Models often use moving boundary conditions to liberate molecules at the interface of inflated rubber and glass phases. The most common drug-release mechanism for hydrogels is diffusion.

Applications in different delivery routes

Hydrogels can change their properties or behaviour in response to various stimuli. Hydrogels are used to address two major issues: Firstly, further *in vivo* study is required to determine how they behave after being implanted in humans. Second, it is critical to develop novel, efficient, and environmentally friendly hydrogel manufacturing techniques. Hydrogels have emerged as unique drug delivery vehicles, particularly for brain or spinal cord injuries, heavy metal removal, tissue engineering, biosensor, regeneration, cancer, bioprinting, soft robots, photonics, fragrance, and the food industry. In the future, it will be profitable to concentrate on the creation of more sophisticated biopolymer-based hydrogels that combine natural polymers with elastin-cellulose and elastin-alginate blends. Such advancements might be extremely beneficial in tissue regeneration.^[16]

Figure 3: Method of Preparation of Hydrogel with applications in different delivery routes.

QUALITY BY DESIGN (QbD) APPROACH

Each element of the QbD approach, as discussed in the reviewed literature, is examined in the subsequent sections.

Quality Target Product Profile (QTPP)

At this phase, the objectives for the intended medicinal product are outlined, considering factors such as clinical application, administration route, type of dosage system, active ingredient concentration, drug stability profile, and additional relevant formulation elements. Typically, at this stage, general and often intuitive objectives are identified, whereas detailed targets are further elaborated within the Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs) section. As shown in Table 1, key elements such as type of dosage system, route of administration, stability parameters, therapeutic strength, and release profiles are consistently considered across most hydrogel-based drug development studies utilizing the QbD approach.

Table 1: Various Quality Target Product Profiles (QTPPs) for hydrogel-based drug delivery systems.

QTPP	TARGET
Mode of Dosage and Drug Transport System	Hydrogel, ^[2] emulgel, ^[17] injectable hydrogel, ^[18] micellar-based in situ gel, ^[19,20] etc
Route Of Administration	Topical, ^[21,22] Oral, ^[23] Dermal, ^[24] Nasal, ^[25] Ocular, ^[19] Intratumoral ^[18]
Dosage strength	Specific drug concentration (e.g., 0.75% metronidazole, 4% niacinamide), ^[17,26]
Stability	Minimum 6–24 months at various storage conditions ^[26]
Container closure system / Packaging	Collapsible opaque tube, amber glass, suitable closure system ^[27]
Method of administration	Once / twice daily application ^[17]
Appearance / Clarity	Smooth, ^[28] transparent, ^[27] or colored gel as appropriate ^[17]
Odor	No unpleasant Odor ^[17,27]
Dosage type / Dosage design/ Drug release	Controlled drug release, ^[29] Rapid release, ^[21] Sustained release, ^[22] Controlled release compared to free drug, ^[28] Modified release.
Viscosity	Acceptable spreadability for the intended application
Method of Preparation	Ionotropic gelation technique
Skin permeation	Higher flux and skin retention (for topical/dermal)
Particle Size	<200–300 nm for nanoparticulate systems
Entrapment/Encapsulation Efficiency	Higher entrapment leads to enhanced permeation
Healing effect/Therapeutic indication/ therapeutic use	Anti-cellulite, skin allergies, local anesthetic, Colon cancer, Anti-inflammatory

pH	Skin-compatible (between 6 & 7) ^[24]
Tsol-Gel temperature / Gelation temperature	30-45°C, depending on application
Gelling Capacity / Gelation Time	Gelation immediately 10–30 min
Elasticity	Elastic and flexible
PDI	Uniform

Critical Quality Attributes (CQA)

CQAs refer to specific physical, chemical, biological, or Microbiological properties of a product or output material, such as a final dosage form, that must be maintained within acceptable limits to guarantee the overall quality of the final product,^[2] Such characteristics, determined through the QTPP and/or prior knowledge, serve as essential benchmarks during product and process development. It is crucial to keep CQAs within specified ranges, limits, or distributions to guarantee that the drug product meets its intended quality standards.^[30] After the QTPPs have been defined, the subsequent stage is to determine the relevant CQAs.^[31] Determining CQAs is a crucial step in any QbD study. CQAs can be determined using prior knowledge and/or through Quality Risk Management (QRM). Such prior knowledge may come from literature reviews, manufacturing history, technology transfer data, stability studies, raw material analyses, adverse event records, and product recall records. In contrast, QRM utilizes structured tools to detect and rank potential CQAs based on risk. As a core component of the QbD approach, QRM facilitates the systematic evaluation of the impact of CMAs and CPPs on CQAs.^[32,33] This, in turn, supports the effective prioritization of CQAs, which is especially crucial in complex manufacturing processes, such as those involving biologics or biosimilars.

Table 2: Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs) Associated with Hydrogel Drug Delivery Formulations.

CQA Parameter	Typical Target/Range	Justification/Role	Limitation
Particle/Globule Size	<100–250 nm (varies by system)	Smaller size improves permeation, skin retention, and drug release	Too small may cause systemic absorption; too large reduces efficacy. ^[2,34]
Entrapment Efficiency	Maximum possible, typically 60-90%	Higher entrapment leads to better drug loading and therapeutic effect	Low entrapment reduces efficacy and may require higher doses ^[34,35]
pH	4.5–7 (skin compatible)	Prevents skin irritation and maintains drug stability	pH outside range can cause irritation or degrade drug ^[4,24]

Viscosity	500–700 × 10 ³ cps (example)	Ensures proper skin retention and controlled release	Too high: poor spreadability; too low: poor retention. ^[27]
Gelation/Sol-Gel Temperature	30–45 °C	Maintains hydrogel integrity at application site	Out-of-range values can hinder in situ gelation or patient comfort ^[36]
Drug Release Profile	Sustained/controlled (e.g., 72 h)	Prolongs therapeutic effect and improves patient adherence	Burst release may cause toxicity; too slow may reduce efficacy ^[23]
Adhesiveness/Elasticity	0.3–1.7 mm (elasticity, example)	Prevents patch breakage and ensures fixation	Poor values lead to detachment or discomfort ^[36,37]
Transmittance	>90% (for SMEDDS gels)	Indicates optical homogeneity and formulation stability	Low transmittance suggests phase separation or instability ^[2,38]
Zeta Potential	>40 mV	Ensures dispersion stability and particle uniformity	Low values risk aggregation and instability ^[39]
Skin Retention/Deposition	High	Maximizes local therapeutic effect and minimizes systemic exposure	Low retention reduces efficacy, especially for topical/wound applications ^[40]
Cumulative Drug Permeation/Flux	High	Ensures adequate drug reaches target tissue	Excessive permeation may cause systemic side effects. ^[40]
Polydispersity Index (PDI)	<0.3	Indicates uniformity of particle size distribution	High PDI leads to instability and inconsistent drug delivery. ^[39]

After the CQAs have been identified, the subsequent step involves determining the factors that have an impact on them. Careful management of these factors helps ensure that the pharmaceutical product meets its intended quality standards. Broadly, the parameters impacting CQAs fall into two main categories: Critical Material Attributes (CMAs) and Critical Process Parameters (CPPs). The following sections provide detailed explanation of each.

Figure 4: QbD Approach: Linking CPPs and CMAs to CQAs.

Critical Material Attributes (CMA)

The physical, chemical, biological, or microbiological characteristics of input materials that need to be kept within particular limits, ranges, or distributions to ensure the desired quality of the therapeutic substance, excipient, or intermediate product are known as critical material attributes, or CMAs.^[41] Closely aligned with the structural and functional components of a formulation, CMAs play a dominant role in modulating the Critical Quality Attributes of hydrogel-based drug delivery systems. Commonly recognized CMAs in hydrogel-based drug delivery systems include the type and quantity of drugs, polymers, cosurfactants, and surfactants. Several studies indicate that CMAs frequently have a greater impact than CPPs on the final formulation's overall performance and quality.

Table 3: Common Critical Material Attributes (CMAs) in the Development of Hydrogel-based Drug Delivery Systems.

CMA Category	Examples	Role/Impact on Hydrogel Performance	Example Systems (Route of Administration)
Polymer Properties	Type, molecular weight, concentration	Determines gel structure, swelling behaviour, mechanical strength, and drug release kinetics.	- Poloxamer 407, Poloxamer 188 ^[42] - HPMC K4M in (ocular gels) ^[43]
Crosslinker	Type, concentration	Controls network density, degradation rate, and drug diffusion.	Sodium alginate/PVA in diabetic wound hydrogels ^[44]
Drug Properties (API)	Solubility, stability, Particle size	Affects drug loading efficiency, release profile, and stability within the hydrogel matrix.	Apremilast (topical), Ketoconazole (topical) ^[2]
Additives/Excipients	Surfactants, stabilizers, pH modifiers	Modulate viscosity, enhance stability, and improve compatibility with the API.	Lipid content in solid lipid nanocarriers ^[28]
Lipid Components	Solid/liquid lipid ratio, total lipid	Influences nanoparticle size, entrapment efficiency, and controlled release in lipid-hybrid gels.	Apremilast-loaded solid lipid nanocarriers embedded hydrogel(topical); ^[2] Ketoconazole cubosomes hydrogel (topical) ^[28]
Water/Solvent	Purity, content	- Water content influences swelling behaviour, gelation, mechanical strength and drug diffusion properties. - Purity is critical to avoid contamination and ensure reproducibility. - Solvent choice and content can affect drug stability and release profile.	- Injectable hydrogels for cardiology, oncology, immunology, wound healing, and pain management (parenteral, subcutaneous, intratumoral). - Ocular hydrogels (topical, intraocular) - Dermal and transdermal hydrogels (topical) ^[45]

Table 3- highlights examples of Critical Material Attributes (CMAs) examined within the context of pharmaceutical systems based on hydrogel. As Illustrated, most QbD-based studies on hydrogels focus on formulations intended for topical drug delivery. These formulations, typically considered Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs), such as particle size, entrapment efficiency, polydispersity index (PDI), drug release profile, and skin retention. Notably, in studies involving topical application, several CMAs have been identified as influential to these CQAs-such as lipid concentration (especially in formulations incorporating lipids as carriers),^[35,46] surfactant concentration,^[35,38,46] and stabilizer concentration.^[28,47]

Critical Process Parameters (CPP)

CPPs are process variables which, when altered within their normal operating range, exert a direct and significant influence on the product's critical quality attributes(CQAs).^[48] As shown in Table 4, several commonly reported Critical Process Parameters (CPPs) involved in the manufacturing of hydrogel-based drug delivery systems include temperature,^[49] stirring speed,^[50] Sonication duration^[46] and homogenization tim.^[51]

Table 4: Critical Process Parameters (CPPs) influence the quality of the hydrogel-based drug delivery system.

CPP	Description & Impact	Delivery System Type	Route of Administration	Impact/Example
Sonication time	Influences particle size reduction, polydispersity, and drug encapsulation efficiency; affects stability and release.	Solid lipid nanocarriers embedded hydrogels	Topical	Sonication time influenced both the particle size and entrapment efficiency of apremilast-loaded solid lipid nanocarriers incorporated in hydrogel (topical). ^[2,46]
Homogenization Time & Speed	Regulates particle size, PDI, drug loading; affects uniformity and stability of nanoemulsions and hydrogels.	Nanoemulsions, nanocarriers	Topical (skin)	Homogenization time and speed influenced particle size and drug loading in econazole nitrate nanosponges and lidocaine/prilocaine nanoemulsions ^[51]
Temperature Control	Controls gelation, polymer crosslinking, drug stability, and viscosity; affects particle size and drug release profile.	Hydrogels, nanocarriers, microspheres	Topical, intranasal, oral	Temperature during dissolution phase influenced hydrodynamic diameter and stability of <i>n</i> -propyl gallate SLN-loaded hydrogels (intranasal) ^[49]
Crosslinking Time	Determines network density, mechanical	Microspheres, IPN microbeads	Oral	Cross-linking time influenced entrapment

	strength, degradation, and drug release kinetics.			efficiency and drug release in chitosan-calcium alginate microspheres for colon delivery. ^[52]
-Stirring Speed - Homogenization time - Homogenization speed	Affects particle size, homogeneity, entrapment efficiency, and viscosity; critical for nanoparticle dispersion in hydrogels.	Nanosponges, lipid nanocarriers, phytosomal gels	Topical	Stirring speed affected particle size and entrapment efficiency in econazole nitrate-loaded β -cyclodextrin nano sponges hydrogel. ^[51]
Microwave Power	Used in microwave-assisted synthesis; it impacts particle size, absorbance, and drug encapsulation efficiency.	Silver nanoparticle-loaded hydrogels	Topical	Microwave power affected particle size and absorbance in chitosan-loaded silver nanoparticle hydrogels. ^[53]
Rotation speed	Affects vesicle size, entrapment efficiency, and homogeneity in liposomal or phytosomal gels.	Phytosomal gels	Topical	Rotation speed controlled vesicle size and entrapment efficiency in phytosomal Manjistha extract gel. ^[54]

Risk Assessment

Risk assessment comprises three key components: risk identification, risk analysis, and risk evaluation. Risk Identification involves systematically gathering and using information to detect potential hazards related to the specific risk question or issue. This process may include reviewing historical data, conducting theoretical analyses, considering expert opinions, and addressing stakeholder concerns. Risk Analysis focuses on estimating the level of risk linked to the identified hazards. Risk Evaluation compares the estimated risks against predefined risk criteria—using either qualitative or quantitative methods - to determine their overall significance.

Risk assessment helps in identifying key parameters that significantly influence critical quality attributes. An initial risk assessment is particularly useful in identifying potential risks linked with hydrogels. A risk estimation matrix is used to assess relationships between different data sets and to identify the area in need of improvement and potential corrective action.^[55]

The design focused on selecting the proper components; therefore, the influencing material quality and process factors were collected and shown on an Ishikawa diagram (Fig.1).^[56] The Ishikawa diagram identifies and groups potential causes to determine the root cause of an issue.

Fig. 5: Factors affecting the quality of a hydrogel-based drug delivery system.

The head of the fish represents the desired quality product in a Fishbone diagram. The broader items (CPP/CMA) are treated as large fishbones, which have thinner fishbones beneath that represent subgroups.

In figure 5, which relates to the methodical identification and analysis of the multifactorial causes of quality variations in hydrogel-based drug delivery systems categorizing them into 6 M categories: Men (Personnel), Machine (Equipment), Material (Raw Materials & APIs), Method (Process Techniques), Measurement (Testing/Validation), and Mother Nature (Environment). Under the Personnel category, factors such as inadequate training, deviation from SOPs, lack of expertise, and improper aseptic handling may compromise product quality. Equipment-related variables, including unqualified machinery, inadequate mixing or blending, and improper speed or temperature control, also contribute significantly. The Material branch highlights critical raw material attributes such as solubility, melting point, incompatibility, and surfactant properties (e.g., HLB value) that influence the final product performance. Process techniques, including gelling method, sterilization, and mixing rate, directly affect CQAs such as particle size, pH, PDI, and entrapment efficiency. The

Measurement segment covers validation parameters that must be consistently monitored, while the Environment or Mother Nature category emphasizes the importance of controlled temperature, humidity, sterility, and storage conditions to maintain formulation stability and prevent microbial contamination. This fishbone structure allows researchers and manufacturers to pinpoint high-risk variables, establish robust control strategies, and enhance overall product reliability through a QbD approach. For example, a study conducted by Rapalli et al., systematically evaluated the formulation and behaviour of solid lipid nanocarriers incorporated in hydrogels for the topical delivery of apremilast. Within the context of a fishbone (Ishikawa) diagram, critical material attributes (CMAs)—such as gelling agents, surfactant types, and hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB)—were mapped as key contributors. These elements, depicted along one of the major branches of the diagram, demonstrated a significant influence on critical quality attributes (CQAs) like entrapment efficiency, particle size distribution (PDI), and zeta potential. This visual representation clearly showed formulation components and their associated product quality implications, underscoring the relevance of structured risk analysis during formulation development.^[46] Then, it becomes necessary to use a method to choose the most effective parameters. This is because, first, an effective simplification of parameters will make the study's outcomes easier to interpret, as introducing additional variables can exponentially increase the number of required experiments. In most common studies, the commonly employed techniques include the Risk Assessment Matrix(RAM)^[56] and the Risk Estimation Matrix(REM).^[38]

TOOLS USED IN HYDROGEL-BASED DRUG DELIVERY

Design of Experiments (DoE)

Design of Experiments (DoE) minimizes the number of experimental trials by examining the interactions between factors, resulting in quicker and more economical formulation development compared to conventional trial-and-error techniques. Selecting an appropriate experimental design is essential for creating a commercially viable product. A well-structured experimental design offers significant benefits, including saving time and promoting cost-efficient production.^[57] In drug delivery systems involving hydrogel, DoE serves a critical function in the optimization of formulation parameters, improving drug loading and release profiles, and ensuring product consistency and effectiveness.

At this stage of development, commonly applied methods include Taguchi,^[58] factorial design,^[59] mixture designs, and response surface methodology. These approaches are used to

systematically plan experiments. After executing the experiments as per the selected design framework, statistical analysis is conducted on the collected data. Based on this analysis, the design space is defined by determining appropriate ranges for all targeted responses. Essentially, the design space comprises sets of values or levels of the independent variables that optimally meet the predetermined quality attributes of the product being studied, using the DoE approach.^[2,60] By employing DoE, researchers can efficiently establish an effective design space that ensures consistent product quality within acceptable material and process variability. Common experimental designs, including full factorial, fractional factorial, and Response Surface Methodology (RSM), have been extensively utilized in hydrogel-based drug delivery studies to achieve robust and optimized formulations. The greatest benefit of applying a design space is that any changes made within the defined ranges are not considered major changes.^[29] This indicates that every input or independent variable has an acceptable range. As long as the values remain within these limits, the finished product will meet the manufacturer's quality requirements.

Principal Component Analysis

The multivariate statistical technique known as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) reduces complicated data sets to a smaller number of uncorrelated principal components by converting correlated variables.^[61] This dimensionality reduction allows for the efficient interpretation of large experimental datasets, which is especially beneficial in the development of hydrogel-based drug delivery systems. PCA plays a crucial role in pinpointing the most influential factors affecting key critical quality attributes (CQAs) such as swelling index, bioadhesion, and mechanical strength.^[62] By uncovering hidden patterns and correlations, PCA facilitates the classification and differentiation of hydrogel batches based on their quality attributes, ensuring consistency throughout production. Additionally, PCA is important in process monitoring and control because it allows for the use of chemometric analysis for interpreting data in real time.^[63] This capability allows for the early detection of variability sources and potential process deviations, thereby supporting proactive quality assurance. PCA improves decision-making during formulation development by condensing complicated information into manageable components. It also provides a comprehensive technique for ensuring the reliability and quality of hydrogel-based drug delivery systems.^[63]

Risk Management Tools

Risk Management is a critical component of the Quality by Design (QbD) paradigm, enabling proactive identification and mitigation of potential failure modes in a hydrogel-based drug delivery system. A variety of methodical tools are frequently used to support this objective. Failure mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA), for instance, prioritizes high-risk process steps and critical material attributes by evaluating their severity, probability of occurrence, and detectability—for example, Chalikwar *et al.*, (2023) applied FMEA and Ishikawa diagrams in nanoemulsion development to identify key process variables impacting entrapment efficiency and particle size.^[64] The Ishikawa (Fishbone) diagram complements this by visually organizing potential sources of variability—construction of fishbone diagrams has been reported in chitosan–alginate bead formulations and hydrogel-based release methodologies to map risk contributors. In addition, risk ranking and filtering approaches, such as risk estimation matrices and ranking CMAs/CPs based on their risk priority number (RPN), enable objective assessment of the relative impact of different formulation or processing parameters on critical quality attributes. Collectively, these risk assessment tools support the development of focused control strategies, reducing the likelihood of unintended variability and ensuring consistent quality across hydrogel formulations.^[2]

Control Strategy

A rigorous control strategy is essential for ensuring that hydrogel-based drug delivery systems consistently meet predefined Quality Target Product Profile (QTPP) criteria. Raw material controls involve establishing precise specification limits for polymers, crosslinkers, solvents, and APIs, as demonstrated in Dalwadi and Patel's thermosensitive, 5-fluorouracil hydrogel study, where polymer grade and concentration were tightly regulated to maintain gelation performance and drug release profiles.^[2,44] During manufacturing, in-process controls (IPCs) play a key role, with parameters such as pH, temperature, viscosity, and gelation time actively monitored—typical examples include real-time rheological and pH tracking to ensure consistent gel structure and performance. Process controls, such as mixing speed, crosslinking conditions, and packaging parameters, are also tightly regulated—for example, ketoconazole-cubosome hydrogels employed factorial design to standardize mixing and gelation, ensuring reproducible particle size and drug entrapment.^[28] Finally, final product testing encompasses evaluating drug content uniformity, mechanical properties, swelling behaviour, and drug release kinetics; numerous QbD-driven studies have incorporated standardized *in vitro* release testing and compression or tensile testing to

confirm product robustness and performance. Together, these control strategies form a comprehensive framework - spanning from raw material qualification to final product validation - ensuring hydrogel drug delivery systems are safe, effective, and reproducible.^[65]

APPLICATION OF QbD IN HYDROGEL FORMULATION

The Implementation of QbD in drug delivery systems based on hydrogel has significantly improved formulation safety, efficacy, and reproducibility. QbD identifies the QTPP and CQAs specific to hydrogels, such as swelling index, gelation time, bioadhesion, mechanical strength, and drug release profile, all of which are required for controlled and site-specific drug delivery.^[2,66] Proper mapping of Critical Material Attributes (CMAs) like polymer type and crosslinker concentration, along with Critical Process Parameters (CPPs) including mixing time, temperature, and pH, is crucial to ensuring consistent hydrogel performance^[44] (Dalwadi and Patel, 2020). Studies on natural polymer-based hydrogels, such as chitosan-alginate systems, have demonstrated controlled swelling and pH-dependent drug release using DoE for formulation optimization^[67] (Medha et al., 2024), while synthetic hydrogels like PEG and PVA have shown sustained drug release with controlled mechanical properties when optimized via response surface methodology^[68] (khan et al., 2022). DoE-based approaches, including factorial and Box-Behnken designs, have been widely applied to optimize polymer ratios, crosslinking density, and drug release kinetics^[69] (Campbell et al., 2019). Additionally, QbD has been effectively utilized in the formulation of stimuli-responsive hydrogels, such as thermosensitive systems for cancer therapy, where DoE helped define the design space for rapid gelation and sustained drug release at body temperature^[70] (Solanki et al., 2024). These examples highlight the flexibility and importance of QbD in designing advanced hydrogel drug delivery platforms.

CHARACTERIZATION TECHNIQUES IN QbD FRAMEWORK

The hydrogel-based drug delivery system must be thoroughly characterized to establish strong correlations between formulation variables, process parameters, and critical quality attributes, as outlined in the Quality by Design (QbD) framework.

Physicochemical analyses, including FTIR, DSC, and SEM, confirm polymer-drug interactions, assess thermal behaviour, and reveal hydrogel microarchitecture. For instance, a multi-responsive chitosan-PVP-TEOS hydrogel study utilized FTIR to verify crosslink formation, while SEM visualized its porous structure and DSC demonstrated thermal stability—leading to successful controlled lidocaine release (~96% over 110 min).^[28] A

broader review identified these techniques as essential when assessing crosslinking modes, phase transitions, and pore structure impact on drug diffusion.^[27]

Rheological and mechanical testing underpin the evaluation of viscoelastic properties and gel strength, which are essential for injectable, 3D-printable, or implantable hydrogels. Methods like frequency sweep rheometry and uniaxial compression tests quantify storage/loss moduli, yield stress, and compressive strength. Emerging techniques, such as Brillouin light scattering and *in situ* rheology–Raman spectroscopy, provide novel ways to monitor mechanical evolution during gelation, offering enhanced precision in process control.^[2,71]

In vitro and *In vivo* drug release studies are core to evaluating hydrogel performance. Standard *in vitro* assays model release kinetics (e.g., Higuchi or Korsmeyer–Peppas), while *in vivo* tests validate therapeutic efficacy. A QbD-optimized ketoconazole cubosome-loaded hydrogel used factorial design to predict release (67% at 24 h) and *ex vivo* permeation (~93%), supporting scale-up reliability. Additionally, dynamic hydrogels with self-tuning transport properties have been shown to minimize burst release and extend duration in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* models.^[72]

Finally, the use of Multivariate Data Analysis (MVDA) techniques such as Partial Least Squares (PLS) and Principal components analysis (PCA)- are essential component of the QbD workflow, allowing the simultaneous interpretation of complex datasets from physicochemical, mechanical, and release characterization.^[2] MVDA supports DoE models in identifying significant variables and monitoring batch consistency in real time, thereby improving product robustness. Collectively, these characterization strategies create a scientifically grounded and quality-focused framework for developing advanced hydrogel drug delivery platforms.^[73]

CHALLENGES AND RESEARCH GAPS

Despite significant advancements, applying QbD to Hydrogel-based drug delivery systems still faces several challenges. A major limitation is a gap between academic and industrial practices, where academic research often remains at the DoE and laboratory level without progressing to pilot-scale production, real-time process analytical technology (PAT) integration, or regulatory documentation. This is mainly due to limited resources and access to advanced equipment. Additionally, there is a critical lack of standardization in hydrogel characterization methods, with variations in porosity, mechanical testing, and self-healing

assessments across laboratories, creating inconsistency and hindering cross-study comparisons. Furthermore, while artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) are growing as strong tools in pharmaceutical development, their application in QbD for hydrogels remains limited. Current challenges include data quality issues, insufficient model transparency, the absence of standardized polymer descriptors, and misalignment with regulatory frameworks like ICH Q2(R2)/Q14. Addressing these gaps will require developing collaborative academic-industrial models, harmonizing hydrogel characterization protocols, and adopting explainable AI (XAI) strategies to improve regulatory acceptance and process predictability. Building polymer informatics databases could further strengthen QbD modeling and enhance reproducibility. Bridging these research gaps will be crucial for the future success of QbD-driven hydrogel drug delivery systems, enabling the development of safer, scalable, and regulatory-compliant products.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

In hydrogel-based drug delivery systems, Quality by Design (QbD) is quickly moving toward more intelligent, environmentally friendly, and patient-specific solutions.^[74] Hydrogel production is anticipated to transform thanks to emerging technologies like digital twins and Process Analytical Technology (PAT), which enable real-time virtual modelling, proactive quality assurance, and predictive process control. Additionally, new opportunities for hydrogel optimization are presented by artificial intelligence (AI)-based formulation design, which uses big data and machine learning to speed up development and increase accuracy. Green chemistry integration into QbD frameworks is also accelerating, with eco-friendly solvents, natural polymers, and biodegradable crosslinkers being added to hydrogel formulations to lessen their negative effects on the environment without sacrificing quality. Additionally, the creation of customized hydrogel treatments through cutting-edge methods like 3D printing and modular design is creating opportunities for drug administration tailored to each patient, where QbD can guarantee product uniformity and customization to meet specific requirements. Recent research on QbD-optimized disulfide-linked hyaluronic acid (HA) hydrogels shows promise for customized therapies with adjustable mechanical and degrading characteristics. All of these advancements enable QbD to be an effective approach for guiding the development of hydrogel drug delivery systems in the future.

CONCLUSION

Developing a hydrogel-based drug delivery system using QbD principles represents a revolutionary approach to pharmaceutical formulation. QbD allows a deep understanding of formulation variables, material attributes, and process parameters, which ultimately leads to more robust, predictable, and patient-centred drug products. Hydrogels, owing to their biocompatibility, tunable properties, and ability to provide controlled and targeted drug release, are particularly well-suited to benefit from QbD-guided development strategies. Through systematic application of QTPP, CQAs, CMAs, and CPPs- along with risk assessment tools such as DoE and multivariate data analysis – formulators can optimize hydrogel systems for a wide range of administration routes and therapeutic applications. Even though there have been a lot of advancements, there are still issues, especially with standardization, scalability, and harmonizing regulations, especially in small companies and university settings.

Looking ahead, the fusion of QbD with emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, digital twins, and process analytical technology (PAT) holds immense potential to streamline hydrogel development. Moreover, the incorporation of sustainable practices and personalized medicine approaches further aligns with the evolving regulatory and patient-care landscape. Future realization of the potential of QbD in the next generation of hydrogel-based therapies will depend on continued interdisciplinary collaboration and innovation.

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